

CORRELATION OF L2 MOTIVATION FACTORS WITH SAUDI EFL UNDERGRADUATE UNIVERSITY LEARNERS' INTENDED EFFORT IN LEARNING L2

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ABSTRACT

This mixed-method study explores factors involving L2 motivation of non-English major Saudi EFL learners and the correlation of these motivating factors with their intended effort to develop English as a second language. Using Dörnyei's L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS), it draws on the perspectives of 129 randomly selected participants, collected using a close-ended questionnaire-based survey and semi-structured interviews with five randomly sampled participants from the survey pool. The findings reveal that the Ideal L2 Self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience emerged as the strongest motivating factors. These two constructs were also significantly correlated with learners' intended effort to learn L2. Conversely, the Ought-to L2 Self, the second principal component of L2MSS, emerged as the least significant motivating factor and appeared to have a weak correlation with intended effort. The study suggests that if teachers use appropriate motivational strategies to enhance learners' Ideal L2 Self-image, they can significantly contribute to the process of L2 learning.

Keywords: English as a Foreign Language; motivation factors; L2 Motivation Self System; L2 learning.

INTRODUCTION

Motivation is considered a complex phenomenon that involves several factors capable of providing impetus to L2 learners for language learning (Eom and Braithwaite, 2023; Printer, 2023). In their seminal work on motivation, Gardner and Lambert (1959; 1972) suggest that a potential successful learner of L2 tries to acquire knowledge of L2 and yearns to integrate into the L2 community. They argue that the desire to

identify and integrate with the ethnolinguistic community of the target language might sustain learners' motivation for a long period required to master L2. Ellis (2015) lists learners' goal to develop L2, their efforts in this project, and their persistency with learning tasks as central motivating triggers. Motivated learners are keen to learn, eager to rehearse what they learn with their classmates or other people

outside the classroom, and their efforts persist consistently over time. The studies in the field of L2 motivation have brought forth interesting aspects in this regard. Broadly, they suggest that motivation is fluid and oscillating, subject to changing contexts, times and situations (Ortega, 2009).

The scholars engaged in investigating L2 motivation have carried out extensive research in various ESL and EFL contexts (e.g., Gardner, 1985; Dörnyei, 2005; Csizér & Kormos, 2009; Ueki & Takeuchi, 2013). Boo, Dörnyei and Ryan (2015) maintain that “the study of L2 motivation has seen an unprecedented boom during the past decade” (p. 145). However, the EFL context of Saudi Arabia is still an under-explored research area in L2 motivation. Therefore, this study explores the components of the L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) that are found to be the L2 motivation of male undergraduate Saudi students of English as a Foreign Language (EFL). Besides, the study investigates the relationship between different components of L2 motivation of male Saudi EFL learners and their Intended Efforts to learn English as a Foreign Language. For this purpose, this study uses Dörnyei’s (2005) L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS). Though there are a few studies that have explored the L2 motivational factors of the students in Saudi Arabia, other than that of Moskovsky et al. (2016), no study has focused on the relationship between L2MSS and the actual proficiency of Saudi students in L2. Notwithstanding the significance of this study, more studies in this context are needed to build a clearer picture of Saudi students’ motivation and the various factors that impact it. This study, which is anchored on the following research questions, is conducted to fill this gap:

RQ 1- What components of the L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) are found as L2 motivation of male Saudi students of English as a Foreign Language (EFL)?

RQ2- What is the relationship between the different components of L2 motivation of male Saudi EFL students and their Intended Efforts to learn English as a Foreign Language?

Context: Many Saudi students learn English as a Foreign Language in almost all major public-sector universities in Saudi Arabia. They study general English in Preparatory Year Programmes (PYP) for one year. In order to continue their studies as undergraduate students, they must pass four levels of English from Level 101 to 104, corresponding to CEFR A1, A2, B1, and B1+. Since this is a mandatory programme, it is a challenging task for teachers to keep these students interested and engaged in the task of learning the L2 during this one-year programme.

Literature Review

Motivation is a complex notion, and researchers in the field of L2 motivation in the context of EFL have been investigating it. During the second half of the twentieth century, the studies in L2 motivation were considerably influenced by the ideas contributed by Gardner and Lambert (1959). They identified two factors which they believe play an important role in the learning process and ultimate achievement in L2: the attitude of L2 learners towards the culture and community of the target language (integrative motivation) and instrumental motivation (Ellis, 2015). Integrative motivation refers to learners’ “aspiration to identify with the speakers of the target language” and allowing “elements of another culture into” their “own life space” (Gardner, 1979, p. 193). On the other hand, instrumental motivation emanates from the practical reasons to learn L2. Dörnyei, Csizér and Nemeth (2006) argue that instrumental motivation is an important aspect of the Ideal L2 Self because “the idealised language self is a cognitive representation of all the incentives associated with L2 mastery; it is also linked to professional competence” (p. 92). According to Ortega (2009), “motivation is usually understood to refer to the desire to initiate L2 learning and the effort employed to sustain it” (p. 168). Motivation is also believed to affect the pace of learning as well as the eventual achievement of learners (Ellis, 2015). In 1985, Gardner presented a socio-educational model of second language

acquisition in which motivation was presented as “the combination of effort plus desire to achieve the goal of learning the language plus favourable attitudes towards learning the language” (p. 10). In this study, we employ Dörnyei’s (2005) L2MSS model to study the question of L2 motivation in the Saudi context. It consists of three principal components: Ideal L2 Self, Ought-to L2 Self, and L2 Learning Experience. This model affords an effective framework for the study of L2 motivation factors. L2MSS does not merely describe L2 motivation; it also helps researchers explore the learning behaviour of L2 learners and identify its features, the relationship among these features, and their probable causes, which are the foci of this study. L2MSS clearly and explicitly states its claims and clarifies what ground it covers. Many research studies in the field of L2 motivation have been conducted employing L2MSS in diverse geographical, cultural, and socioeconomic contexts (see Csizér & Kormos, 2009; Lamb, 2009 & 2012; Islam et al., 2013; Ueki & Takeuchi, 2013; You & Dörnyei, 2014; Moskovsky et al., 2016). Therefore, this model is expected to efficiently explore the dimensions/features of L2 motivation of Saudi EFL learners.

Surahio, Rashidi, Nadeem (2025) say that tools such as Applicant Tracking Systems (ATS), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and predictive analytics contribute significantly to enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of recruitment processes, aligning with global trends. However, the study also uncovers concerns regarding potential biases within these systems, underscoring the necessity of periodic monitoring and updates to maintain fairness. These findings suggest that while TAR tools are integral to the modern evolution of recruitment practices in Karachi’s banking sector, further research and development are crucial to fully realizing their potential.

Ideal L2 Self

The Ideal L2 Self is the learners’ ideal future self-image as a competent user of L2. Here, learners focus on promotion because their behaviour is driven by an outcome that is

either enjoyable/desirable or practical, or both. Strongly motivated learners of L2, according to Dörnyei (2005), have an ideal of their L2 self, i.e., they aspire to achieve proficiency in L2 in future and are willing to employ efforts to achieve that ideal. If a learner perceives a discrepancy between his current L2 self and the future ideal L2 self, it motivates him to resolve the discrepancy to achieve his Ideal L2 Self. In other words, they desire to “close the gap or discrepancy between the actual self and the ideal self” (Ortega, 2009, p. 186). Kramsch (2006) recognizes the music of the target language as one of the factors that can contribute to the formation of the Ideal L2 Self in L2 learners (p. 102). It can stimulate adolescent language learners’ imagination because their identity formation is in progress. Dörnyei, Csizér and Nemeth (2006) link instrumental motivation to Ideal L2 Self. It means the imagined ideal self of learners is desirable for them because it represents their expected L2 competence in the future, which can help them be successful in their careers. Ideal L2 Self has been found to be a strong motivational factor in university students. Papi (2010) discovered that the Ideal L2 Self was a significant factor influencing the language learning behaviour/Intended Effort in Iranian university students. Islam, Lamb, and Chambers’ (2013) study also confirmed that the Ideal L2 Self had a significant effect on Pakistani university learners’ Intended Effort to learn L2. Csizér and Kormos (2009) also found that Ideal L2 Self significantly motivated Hungarian university students and played a vital role in the Intended Efforts (motivated behaviour) to learn L2. However, the Ideal L2 Self did not emerge as a clear motivational factor among young learners. According to Csizér and Kormos (2009), this difference suggested that psychological factors, which might not be important in childhood and early adolescence in secondary school students, could play a stronger role in the later stages of adolescence in university students. Moskovsky et al.’s (2016) research focused on Saudi male and female EFL learners at two public sector universities in Saudi Arabia. The results of this survey

study also confirmed the existence of a strong relationship between the Ideal L2 Self of learners and their Intended Effort to learn English.

Ought-to L2 Self

Ought-to L2 Self is the self-image of a learner as an L2 learner/user which they believe they ought to possess to avoid undesirable consequences, meet the expectations and win the approval of others, i.e., parents, peers, teachers, boss and society. Dörnyei and Ushioda (2011) maintain that the L2 learning experience represents “situated, ‘executive’ motives related to the immediate learning environment and experience (e.g. the impact of the teacher, the curriculum, the peer group or the experience of success” (p. 86). On the contrary, regarding Ought-to L2 self, the learners’ behaviour is driven by prevention orientations. They exert their efforts to learn L2 to prevent something undesirable or painful, for example, disappointing parents, failing to qualify for admission to a college/university, or facing embarrassment at the workplace. In many research studies, the ought-to L2 Self did not emerge as a strong motivational factor. However, where it was found, it seemed to be strongly correlated with high levels of anxiety in learners. Dörnyei, Csizér, and Nemeth (2006) did not find this motivational factor significant in Hungarian school children. Similarly, Lamb (2012) explored the L2 motivation of learners aged between 13-14 years in Indonesia, and in his findings, the Ought-to self was not clearly identified. Kormos and Csizér (2009), and You and Dörnyei (2014) found its presence marginal in Hungarian and Chinese university students, respectively. Also, Taguchi et al. (2009) found a moderate correlation between the Ought-to Self and the Intended Effort of learners from China, Japan, and Iran. Moreover, Moskovsky et al. (2016) confirmed a weak relationship between Ought-to L2 Self and Intended Effort in Saudi students. The research findings of Ueki and Takeuchi (2013) and Papi (2010) in Japanese and Iranian EFL contexts, respectively, confirmed that the learners

who were motivated by Ought-to Self also showed a significant level of anxiety, and this negatively affected their efforts to learn L2.

Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience

The third principal construct of Dörnyei’s L2MSS is the Language Learning Experience, also known as Attitude to Learning. This experience consists of relationships with peers, classroom environment, teaching material, teachers’ teaching style and their attitude towards learners. In all the research studies discussed in the above sections, this motivational factor played the most significant role in motivating learners of all ages to learn L2. Its correlation with the language learning behaviour, or Intended Effort of learners to learn L2, was also found as the most significant in all the above-mentioned studies. However, the findings of Taguchi et al. (2009)’s study were slightly different. Although the role of language learning experience in motivating learners to invest efforts in the learning process of L2 was significant in Japanese and Iranian students, for Chinese learners, this did not make much difference. The researchers explained this difference by pointing out that there was enormous pressure on Chinese students because of their socioeconomic situation. Therefore, they could not afford to let a suboptimal classroom learning environment hinder their efforts to achieve their goal of proficiency in English or passing their English language exams.

Methodology

This mixed-method study included a structured bilingual questionnaire (Arabic + English) based survey and semi-structured interviews. The participants (n=129) were Arabic-speaking male Saudi national undergraduate university students aged between 18 and 21. In the Preparatory Year Programme (PYP) classes, they were studying general English as a Foreign Language for 18 hours a week. The study used a probability sampling technique where participants were randomly selected from different English language sections of level 104 (CEFR B1+).

Altogether 129 learners completed the questionnaire, and after excluding nine questionnaires with insufficient data, the final sample size was 120. These students had studied and passed English levels 101, 102, and 103 (corresponding to CEFR levels A1, A2, and B1) in previous modules in the same institute.

Questionnaire-Based Survey

The questionnaire-based survey was conducted to collect quantitative data to find answers to RQ 1 and 2, i.e., to explore and identify motivational factors of these EFL learners within the framework of L2MSS and their relationship with Intended Effort. The questionnaire was adapted from You and Dörnyei (2014), which they used to investigate the motivational dispositions of Chinese learners. There were 29 six-point Likert scale items with six responses in the instrument - 1st stood for strongly disagree and 6th, strongly agree. The questions included in the instrument were focused on (a) dimensions of the L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) and (b) the criterion measure of Intended Effort. The English version of the questionnaire was translated into Arabic by a qualified professional translator, and the Arabic version was then back-translated by another professional translator. The questions in the instruments

were given both in Arabic and English. A total of 129 participants completed the paper-based survey for this study.

The raw data was keyed in IBM SPSS Version 24. Before starting the analyses, data was checked for errors and outliers. As suggested by (Dörnyei, 2007), to “reduce the number of variables to a manageable size”, the items that focused on specific components of the L2 Motivational Self System (L2MSS) were “summed up in “multi-item scales” for analysis (p. 206). The Mean (M) of the interrelated questions was calculated in SPSS (see Table 1). After creating broad variables, Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficient was calculated for each broad variable to check for the internal consistency reliability to test correlation in the items that were grouped together. Since the recommended minimum figure is 0.70 (Dörnyei, 2007), only those items with a coefficient value of 0.70 or above were included in further analyses as a result of the internal consistency reliability check, Instrumentality Promotion and Instrumentality Prevention variables were excluded from the subsequent analyses because the reliability coefficient figures were far below the recommended value of 0.70.

Table 1 Summary of motivational variables, mean and Cronbach’s reliability score

Variables	Number of items	Frequency Mean	Cronbach’s Alpha Reliability Coefficients	Question Number
Ideal L2 Self	5	5.03	.79	5, 10, 17, 20, 25
Instrumentality Promotion	3	5.46	.49	3, 13, 15
Ought-To L2 Self	8	3.74	.82	1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9, 19,22
Instrumentality Prevention	4	4.55	.48	11, 14, 21, 24
Attitude towards learning English (L2 Learning Experience)	5	4.51	.84	4, 12, 16, 18, 23
Intended Effort	4	5.27	.70	26, 27, 28, 29

Note: Question number 22 in Ought-To Self was omitted, as suggested by Cronbach Alpha Analysis, to improve the reliability (Dörnyei, 2007). It was not included in the subsequent analyses.

Semi-Structured Interviews

Individual interviews with five randomly selected learners from the survey pool were conducted in English to profoundly explore the emerging motivation factors. The interview questions were based on the questions used in a research project by Harrison (2009) and were adapted to suit

the context of this inquiry. The interviews were semi-structured; therefore, the questions only served as prompts to explore the L2 motivational aspects of learners with the main focus on the research questions of this study. Two devices, iPhone 7 Plus and Sony IC Recorder ICD-UX543F were used to avoid any issues of unclear voice in the recording or loss of data due to any unforeseen incident.

After the interview responses were transcribed, the data was read several times for an overview. During this process, notes and comments were written in margins, and the main ideas were highlighted, as suggested by Agar (1980) and Cohen et al. (2011). After exploring the data in general, coding was carried out by following the steps recommended by Creswell (2012). The relevant parts of the texts were labelled with codes which, then, were studied and examined to collapse similar codes in broad themes (Creswell, 2012). After this step of coding, the transcripts were once again examined to see if there were other aspects which could be labelled under new codes. Data was also sifted to find the specific quotes which supported codes and those quotes were categorized with the relevant codes and themes.

Findings

Results of the Questionnaire-Based Survey

The analysis of factors, that motivated L2 male Saudi learners of English as a Foreign Language (EFL), and of the relationship of identified L2MSS components with their Intended Effort, suggests an overall positive disposition of learners towards learning English as L2. The descriptive statistical details of the four variables are given in Table 2. The mean (M) values of all the variables related to the three components of L2MSS ranged from 3.74 to 5.03 on a six-point scale. The mean values of Ideal L2 Self and Intended Effort were the highest and almost identical, which indicated the learners had strong Ideal L2 selves and strong intentions to exert efforts to learn L2. Similar findings were shown for Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience with a Mean value considerably above the midpoint, 3.50. This explains that the Language Learning Experience was the second most powerful motivating factor in these learners. Ought-to L2 Self had the lowest Mean value among all four variables. It was just above the midpoint, which suggests a weak presence for this motivational factor in learners.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics about the motivational variables

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Ideal L2 Self	120	5.03	.748
Ought-to L2 Self	120	3.74	1.020
Attitude to Learning/ Language Learning Experience	120	4.51	1.003
Intended Effort/ Language learning behaviour	120	5.01	.757
Valid N (listwise)	120		

Note: A low standard deviation means that most of the numbers are very close to the average. A high standard deviation means that the numbers are spread out.

To examine the relationship between three principal motivational variables of L2MSS i.e., Ideal L2 Self, Ought-to L2 Self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience, and Intended Effort to learn L2, Spearman's rho correlation coefficients were obtained via SPSS version 24 (see Table 3). Referring to the meaningful strength value

of correlation coefficient, Dörnyei (2007, p. 223) maintains, "in applied linguistic research we can find meaningful correlations of as low as 0.3-0.5". The results showed the correlation between Attitude to learning/Language Learning Experience and the Intended Effort of participants as the most significant ($r=.578$). The correlation between Ideal L2 Self and Intended Effort ($r=.488$) closely followed the preceding result. Both these correlation coefficient values were significant and they showed a

strong correlation between these two components and learners' Intended Effort. This suggests that the learners who were motivated by Ideal L2 Self and Language Learning Experience, also showed strong intentions to invest efforts to learn L2. The correlation between Ought-to L2 Self and

Intended Effort variable was identified but it was weak and therefore, less significant ($r = .214$), which indicates that the learners motivated by Ought-to L2 Self did not show willingness to employ much effort to learn L2.

Table 3 Spearman's rho correlations between the three components of the L2MSS (the principal motivational variables) and Intended Effort/Language learning Behaviour

	Variables		Intended Effort
Spearman's rho	Ideal L2 Self	Correlation Coefficient	.488**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	120
	Ought to Self	Correlation Coefficient	.214*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.019
		N	120
	Attitude to Learning	Correlation Coefficient	.578**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		N	120
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).			

Results of the Interviews

The qualitative data obtained from students' interviews displayed similar trends as the quantitative data. The Ideal L2 Self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience were significant L2 motivational factors that contributed to students' motivation to learn L2. Also, these two factors were significantly correlated with the criterion measure, Intended Effort. No participant mentioned the purpose of learning the English language due to the extrinsic pressure from their families or society at large. Hence, Ought-to L2 does not cast any significant influence on learners to learn English as a Foreign Language.

Ideal L2 Self

In the interview, Ahmed mentioned that what made him enjoy the English language courses was the vision of his future self: "when I study English, I imagine myself in the future, how I will be... that's why I enjoy when I take the courses." Role models that students see in real life and/or characters in TV shows or movies, have the potential to make a considerable impact on Ideal L2 Self of learners (Dörnyei, 2009). Some learners

looked at these role models as guides or a standard they aspire to achieve in their L2 proficiency. They would like to use/speak L2 as their role models do. Ahmed expressed this wish in the following words: "I want to talk like [the people in] the movies and the people who talk in English like an American, British." Hassan, described his experience of visualizing his future self, when he would be able to use English, as "Sensational." "When I imagine myself speaking English without grammar mistakes using complicated word(s)." "Yes, usually this [is] what comes to my mind because I always imagine myself studying abroad so apparently [these] two things [are] connected. Studying outside [abroad] and speaking English (inaudible) freely." Faisal said, "I feel good. I imagine it and I feel like it's something good if [I] will speak good [well] and my accent will be good." These three participants had a clear vision of their Ideal L2 Self, which made them see/imagine what they would be like in future if they developed a certain level of proficiency in L2.

The importance of English as a global language emerged as a prominent theme from students' interview data. This

suggested that students strongly recognized the importance of English, particularly in view of it being the formal language of instruction at Saudi and international universities (see Alshahrani et al., 2012; Al-Seghayer, 2012). They consider English as an important L2 to become members of global educational and professional communities. Ahmed said that he felt pressured to learn English “just for my future and my future job. You need [to be a] good speaker and to talk with other doctors.” Faisal believed that learning English was important, “because it’s [an] international language and everybody speak[s] it. If I travel to another country, all speak English. It’s second language for anybody.” “I want to learn just because it is very important now and in future, it will be important for me.” Asif also had similar reasons to learn English, “I choose English because it’s the most common language in the world.” Ahmed said that he wanted to study medicine and English would be “very important to be a professional doctor and it will help me in my study and research.” To Hassan, proficiency in English would distinguish him from other candidates for the jobs he would like to apply for in future, “especially for those jobs [where] many candidates come, usually what distinguish between candidates is English. If you want to get [a] job, you have to have English.” Nasir also wanted to learn English because it would facilitate him in his studies at the medical school, “my aim is to be in a medical school. English is fundamental to the process in the medical school.” The choice of career played an important role in motivating Faisal to learn English, “I want to be a manager and English is important.” All participants believed that learning English would be important for their studies and their professional life.

Attitude to L2 Learning/ Language Learning Experience

The second self-reported significant motivational factor was students’ Language Learning Experience. Four out of five interviewees reported that they enjoyed the process of learning English either inside or

outside the classroom. Ahmed enjoyed the process of learning L2 in English language courses because it would help him become a competent user of English. He also liked listening to his “doctor” because it gave him an authentic listening practice. (Saudi students in universities usually call all their teachers, “doctors”) “I like especially when the doctor is talking in English because I can try to understand the words and sentences.” Nasir also enjoyed the authentic listening experience in class, “inside the class I enjoy it. I enjoy listening to the doctor.” Hassan enjoyed the learning experience inside the classroom as well as outside when he practiced speaking English. “I enjoy both of them. Especially the one outside because it is free [he means there are no formal restrictions as there are in the classroom]. “I like speaking to myself especially in front of the mirror. I like to use new words because usually I spend my time reading dictionaries. Learning new vocabulary. I use them in front of the mirror. I just invent a conversation.” For Asif, his own interest in the English language, his teachers and his classmates make the process of learning interesting. “I choose English because it’s the most common language in the world and everybody now speak it. All the subjects are in English and also, I enjoy it.” “I think in the class it depends on the people and also the teacher. In this class, I have a great teacher and great classmates.”

Intended Effort/ Language Learning Behaviour

The third significant theme was the self-reported Intended Effort to learn English as an L2. This theme reflects how much effort learners are willing to invest in learning the L2 as a result of the motivating factors mentioned above. When Ahmed was asked about his strategies to learn English, he answered, “I watch movies without translation to understand what they say and I read news in English language and sometimes [I] listen to English music.” Similarly, Hassan also had some strategies to improve proficiency in English. “Well, I do normal activities. I like reading books and going to dictionaries and things like that.

What I do especially is I watch programmes with no subtitles, no help. Nothing!” Hassan also mentioned an interesting practice for improving his speaking skills. “I like speaking to myself, especially in front of the mirror. I like to use new words because usually I spend my time reading dictionaries. Learning new vocabulary. I use them in front of the mirror. I just invented a conversation.” Faisal and Asif, like Ahmed, used similar strategies to improve their proficiency in English. When asked what he would do if he was not able to develop his desired level of proficiency in English, he replied, “...I will work harder to be successful in it and achieve it.” Nasir: “Obviously I will be sad, bitter and down feeling in my spirits but I will try to learn English.” Faisal: “Yeah, I will keep working to learn English. I don’t want to stop.” Asif: “Of course I will be very sad but it won’t stop me. I will keep trying until I succeed in my English.” Hence, all participants were motivated enough to keep learning even if they were unsuccessful in their attempts.

Discussion

The findings of the study demonstrated that the Ideal L2 self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience were the two strongest motivational factors for L2 in participants. Attitude to learning/L2 learning experience had the second highest Mean value, suggesting that the learners were strongly motivated by the immediate experience of the L2 learning process. The results of the correlation analysis of L2 motivational factors and criterion measure of Intended Effort suggested that Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience and Ideal L2 Self contributed significantly to Intended Effort, i.e., in motivating learners to invest their efforts to learn L2. On the other hand, the correlation between Ought-to L2 Self and Intended Effort showed that Ought-to L2 Self motivation played a limited role in predicting the effort these learners employed in L2 learning as its relation to Intended Effort was very weak. In other words, the learners who were motivated by this L2 motivational factor did

not show intention to expend much effort to learn L2. Similarly, the interview data also indicated Ideal L2 self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience to be significant motivational factors, and the theme of learners’ Intended Effort also emerged as a significant indicator of all the interviewees’ intention to pursue their goal of learning English. In quantitative data, Ought-to L2 Self was the least significant factor, and a similar trend was reflected through interview data. Below, we discuss these results in relation to each component of L2MSS.

Ideal L2 Self and Attitude to Learning

The Ideal L2 self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience emerged as strong L2 motivational factors among the sampled Saudi EFL students. In the descriptive statistics, the Mean values of the three principal components of L2MSS in Table 3 were above the midpoint value, i.e., 3.50, which suggested an overall positive disposition of the learners towards learning English as L2. Another factor that indicated learners’ considerable interest and commitment to learning the L2 was the high scale value of Intended Effort ($M = 5.01$). The Ideal L2 Self has the highest Mean value among the principal components of L2MSS, which suggests that the participants of this study had a strong Ideal L2 self-image, motivating them to learn L2. These results are consistent with Csizér and Kormos’s study (2009), which found Ideal L2 Self and Language Learning Experience as two significant L2 motivational factors, which both significantly contributed to Intended Effort.

Ideal L2 Self and Intended Effort

The vision of the future Ideal L2 Self was one aspect of the learners’ Ideal L2 Self in this study. The results obtained through Spearman’s rho test in SPSS version 24 of correlation analysis of the L2 motivational factors and the criterion measure of Intended Effort suggested that Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience and the Ideal L2 Self contributed significantly to Intended Effort. Three out

of 5 interviewees reported that they did imagine their future Ideal L2 selves. The tendency towards the Ideal L2 Self is also apparent in the learners' desire to speak like their ideals, i.e., the characters in movies, newscasters, singers etc., and in ideals of instrumental achievements, reflected in their desire to learn English to be successful in their studies and future professions; and to be a part of the global community by learning English as a Global Language (EGL). An extensive study conducted by Dörnyei et al. (2006) in Hungary that focused on five target languages found that learners ranked English as the most important language to learn because of its importance as a Global Language (EGL). A similar opinion was reflected in the interview samples of this study, and the correlation between the Ideal L2 Self and the Intended Effort was found to be significant in the findings of this study, too. Thus, this study confirmed the finding of Csizér and Kormos (2009)'s study, which states that the Ideal L2 Self of non-English major university students was found to be strongly correlated with the motivated language behaviour, i.e., Intended Effort to learn L2. Three interviewees, Asif, Ahmed and Faisal, also mentioned that they listened to English music to learn English, which reflected their motivation and commitment to learning L2. According to Dörnyei and Kubanyiova (2014), learners with clear Ideal L2 Self usually work hard and consistently employ efforts in difficult tasks to learn L2. Kramersch (2006) argues that the effect of the rhythm of music, sounds of the foreign language and the cool image of the native speakers encourage teenage learners to "strive to enter new, exotic worlds" (p. 102). This study further confirmed the significant correlation between Ideal L2 Self and Intended Effort.

Ought-to L2 Self and Intended Effort

Ought-to L2 is an extrinsic motivational factor related to expectations by society. The learner motivated by this factor expends efforts to learn L2 to avoid undesirable results, for example, disappointing family or failing an exam. This component of L2MSS

emerged only in the quantitative data, and it was the least significant among the three principal components. Its correlation with the criterion measure, i.e., Intended Effort, was also weak. None of the participants during interviews mentioned anything which would suggest that they were learning English to prevent something undesirable from happening or they were doing it to fulfil social expectations. Dörnyei, Csizér, and Nemeth (2006) found only a marginal role of Ought-to L2 Self in Hungarian learners. Similarly, Csizér and Kormos (2009) also found a limited correlation between Ought-to L2 Self and Intended Efforts employed by Hungarian university students. They suggested that the learners in Hungary, from a very young age, were surrounded by products of English business and social culture through foreign investment and multinational companies. This milieu made the children realize that their professional success was dependent on their competence in the English language. These factors, thus, facilitated the gradual internalization of the values associated with the advantage of proficiency in the English language. Consequently, by the age of 16, learning English became part of their desired Ideal L2 Self and the role of external expectations of significant others and social pressure diminished. This seems to be the most likely explanation of the limited role of the Ought-to L2 Self displayed by the Saudi students. For almost the last two decades, the presence of multi-national enterprises and the availability of the products of Western mass media have gradually raised the awareness in Saudi Arabia's young generation that English is important for their successful educational and professional lives (Al-Seghayer, 2012). The government has also played a key role in this change by introducing Preparatory Year Programmes in all major public-sector universities (Al-Seghayer, 2012). These factors, perhaps, have contributed to internalising the otherwise extrinsic motivational factors of learning English to fulfil the expectations of employers, parents or family. Saudi students realize that proficiency in English is important for their educational and

professional careers, and they also enjoy a high social status in their society (Moskovsky et al., 2016). Therefore, if they achieve the goal of Ideal L2 Self by developing proficiency in the English language, it can enable them to be successful students and professionals, which can correspondingly help them earn respect in society.

Attitude to Learning and Intended Effort

The Mean value of this construct of L2MSS was slightly lower than the Mean for the Ideal L2 Self in descriptive statistical results. This suggests that among the three principal constructs of L2MSS, this motivational factor was the second most important factor found in the learners of this study. The correlation of this variable with Intended Effort was the most significant among the three motivational factors. This strong correlation suggested that the positive Language Learning Experience was the strongest predictor of the Intended Effort the learners were willing to employ in their learning of L2. In interview data, four out of five participants stated that they enjoyed the L2 learning experience inside and outside the classroom. Their statements showed a generally positive learning experience inside the classroom. They did not give specific details as to what aspects they particularly enjoyed during the formal language learning process inside the classroom, for example, language learning activities, the teacher's instructional method, or the contents of the prescribed books. Two participants said that they enjoyed listening to their teacher. Another participant mentioned that since they had a good teacher and classmates, they were enjoying the learning process inside the class. So, the positive learning experience depended upon the teacher and the other students. The findings of this study regarding this construct are similar to those of previous studies. Taguchi, Magid and Papi's (2009) investigation found a strong correlation between Attitude to Learning and Intended Effort in Iranian and Japanese learners. On the basis of the findings of their investigation, Csizér and Kormos (2009) argued that the positive learning experience of learners, especially in the

classroom, seemed to affect learners' self-respect and also contributed to their Intended Effort. Lamb (2012) maintains that in addition to the positive learning experience in the formal learning setting of the classroom, "the potential enjoyment to be gained by learning outside school, for example through listening, watching or reading English language media, is also a contributory factor" (p. 1014). The overall language learning experience of the participants in his study was significantly correlated with the Intended Effort.

Conclusion

The most significant motivational factors of the Saudi learners were Ideal L2 Self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience. These were also significantly correlated with learners' Intended Effort. However, Ought-to L2 Self emerged as the least significant motivation factor, and its correlation with Intended Effort was also weak. In other words, the learners motivated by Ideal L2 Self and Attitude to Learning/Language Learning Experience seemed willing to invest significant effort to learn English as L2. In contrast, the learners motivated by the Ought-to L2 Self did not appear willing to employ much effort to learn L2. The findings of this research study concur with many previous research studies in the L2 motivation field, which were carried out in other EFL contexts (e.g., Csizér & Kormos, 2009; Lamb, 2009; Taguchi et al., 2009; Ushioda, 2011). These findings also correspond with the results of the studies conducted in Iran, Pakistan, China and Saudi Arabia by Papi (2010), Islam et al. (2013), You and Dörnyei (2014) and Moskovsky et al. (2016), respectively. Moreover, in all these studies, Ought-to L2 Self was the least significantly correlated with Intended Effort. Similarly, the study shows that L2MSS is suitable for exploring learners' L2 motivation factors and the correlation of these factors with learners' Intended Effort to learn English as L2 in the Saudi EFL context. The research holds significance regarding pedagogical strategies based on these motivations. Further exploration in ELT could be directed towards the constructs of the Ideal L2 Self

and Attitude to Learning in longitudinal studies that may provide insights into the lasting effects of language learning over time, contributing to more comprehensive educational policies in English.

REFERENCES

- Agar, M. H. (1980). *The professional stranger: An informal introduction to ethnography*. San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- Al-Seghayer, K. (2012). Status and functions of English in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Gazette*. Retrieved from <http://64.65.60.109/index.cfm?method=home.regcon&contentid=20121211145659>. Accessed January 5, 2023.
- Alshahrani, K., & Al-Shehri, Saleh. (2012). Conceptions and responses to e-learning: The case of EFL teachers and students in a Saudi Arabian university. *Monash University Linguistics Papers*, 8(1), 21.
- Anderman, E. M., & Anderman, L. H. (2010). *Classroom motivation*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Merrill.
- Boo, Z., Dörnyei, Z., & Ryan, S. (2015). L2 motivation research 2005–2014: Understanding a publication surge and a changing landscape. *System*, 55, 145-157.
- Cohen, L., Manion, L., & Morrison, K. (2007). *Research methods in education*. London: Routledge.
- Creswell, J. (2012). *Educational research (4th ed.)*. Boston, M.A.: Pearson Education.
- Csizér, K., & Kormos, J. (2009). Learning experiences, selves and motivated learning behaviour: A comparative analysis of structural models for Hungarian secondary and university learners of English. In Z. Dörnyei & E. Ushioda (Eds.), *Motivation, language identity and the L2 self* (pp. 98-119). Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Csizér, K., & Lukács, G. (2010). The comparative analysis of motivation, attitudes and selves: The case of English and German in Hungary. *System*, 38(1), 1-13.
- Dörnyei, Z. (2005). *The psychology of the language learner: Individual differences in second language acquisition*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Kubanyiova, M. (2014). *Motivating learners, motivating teachers*. Cambridge, GB: Cambridge University Press.
- Dörnyei, Z., & Ushioda, E. (2011). *Teaching and researching motivation (2nd ed.)*. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Ellis, R. (2015). *Understanding Second Language Acquisition (2nd ed.)*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Eom, M & Braithwaite, J. (2023). Motivation to learn Korean as L2 or L3 in a bilingual, bicultural community. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 1-8. DOI: [10.1080/14790718.2023.2170381](https://doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2023.2170381)
- Gardner, R. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitude and motivation*. London: Edward Arnold.
- Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1959). Motivational variables in second-language acquisition. *Canadian Journal of Psychology*, 13, 266-272.
- Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. E. (1972). *Attitudes and motivation in second language learning*. Rowley, MA: Newbury House.
- Gardner, R.C. (1979). Social psychological aspects of second language acquisition. In H. Giles & R. St Clair (Eds.), *Language and social psychology* (pp. 193–220). Oxford: Blackwell.
- Harrison, J. (2008). Research Project. INNERVATE-Leading undergraduate work in English studies. The University of Nottingham, School of English Studies (pp.109-126). Retrieved from <https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/english/documents/innervate/0809/0809harrisonjpsychologysecondlanguageacquisition.pdf>.
- Islam, M., Lamb, M., & Chambers, G. (2013). *The L2 Motivational Self*

- System and National Interest: A Pakistani perspective. *System*, 41, 231-244.
- Kramsch, C. (2006) Preview article: The multilingual subject. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 16(1), 97-110.
- Lamb, M. (2009). Situating the L2 self: Two Indonesian school learners of English. In Z. Dörnyei & E. Ushioda (Eds.), *Motivation, language identity and the L2 self* (pp. 229-247). Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Lamb, M. (2012) A Self System Perspective on Young Adolescents' Motivation to Learn English in Urban and Rural Settings. *Language Learning*, 62, 997-1023.
- Moskovsky, C., Assulaimani, T., Racheva, S., & Harkins, J. (2016). The L2 motivational self-system and L2 achievement: A study of Saudi EFL learners. *The Modern Language Journal*, 100, 641-654.
- Ortega, L. (2009). *Understanding Second Language Acquisition*. New York: Routledge.
- Papi, M. (2010). The L2 motivational self-system, L2 anxiety, and motivated behaviour: A structural equation modelling approach. *System*, 38, 467-479.
- Papi, M., & Abdollahzadeh, E. (2011). Teacher motivational practice, student motivation, and possible L2 selves: An examination in the Iranian EFL context. *Language Learning*, 62(2), 571-594.
- Printer, L. (2023). Positive emotions and intrinsic motivation: A self-determination theory perspective on using co-created stories in the language acquisition classroom. *Language Teaching Research*, 0(0). <https://doi.org/10.1177/13621688231204443>
- Surahio, Rashidi, Nadeem (2025). A REVIEW OF TECHNOLOGY IN RECRUITMENT: QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY. *JOURNAL OF APPLIED LINGUISTICS AND TESOL (JALT)* 8 (1), 1262-1269
- Taguchi, T., Magid, M., & Papi, M. (2009). The L2 motivational self-system among Japanese, Chinese and Iranian learners of English: A comparative study. In Z. Dörnyei & E. Ushioda (Eds.), *Motivation, Language Identity and the L2 Self* (pp. 66-97). Bristol: Multilingual Matters.
- Ueki, M., & Takeuchi, O. (2013). Forming a clearer image of the ideal L2 self: the L2 Motivational Self System and learner autonomy in a Japanese EFL context. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 7, 238-252.
- Ushioda, E. (2011). Language learning motivation, self and identity: current theoretical perspectives. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 24(3), 199-210. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09588221.2010.538701>
- You, C., & Dörnyei, Z. (2014). Language learning motivation in China: Results of a large-scale stratified survey. *Applied Linguistics*, 37(4), 495-519.